

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

CHRISTIAN A. DIAZ, DM-HRM

INSTRUCTOR III

Negros Oriental State University

diazxtian1984@gmail.com

“CLASSROOM OF LOVE”

In the classroom of their married life,
The teacher, of course, is the loving wife.
With chalk in hand and lesson plan,
She lectures loud as only she can!

“Pick up your socks!” she starts the day,
“Don’t leave your plate and walk away!”
She quizzes him on what she said
But he just grins and scratches his head.

She gives him notes: *“Buy rice today.”*
He nods... then brings ice cream anyway.
She points, she scolds, she rolls her eyes,
While he pretends, he’s *just surprised*.

The husband sits in his favorite chair,
Like a student lost in blank-eyed stare.
Mid-lecture three, he starts to doze
She taps her foot, he strikes a pose.

He fails the quiz, forgets the test,
Yet still insists, *“But I try my best!”*
And when she asks what chapter’s due,
He shrugs, “It’s love... no rules for two.”

She marks his grade with gentle care,
Though he repeats the same errors there.
Still, in her eyes, she lets it slide
She’s teacher, wife, and loving guide.

And though her "student" strays off track,
He always finds his way right back.
For love, you see, is more than smart
It's passing life with all your heart.

